

Determinant Factors of Retail Trading Company Funding Decision to Reduce Company Financial Distress

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ABSTRACT

Retail trading companies are one of the pioneers in supporting Indonesia's GDP growth with a contribution of 12.56%, and still making a high and positive contribution in the first quarter of 2020. A high contribution does not guarantee that the company's financial condition is adequate. BPS data (2020) shows that there was a decline in revenue for trading companies during the pandemic. Companies must establish appropriate funding policies to improve efficient business operations so as not to experience financial distress that could potentially bankrupt. This study aims to analyze the determinants in determining funding that can reduce the financial distress of retail trading companies. The data used are the financial statements of retail companies from 2018 and 2019 with the method used is descriptive quantitative. Path analysis method to analyze hypotheses using the SME model in SPSS AMOS 26. The results of this study indicate; (i) company size 0.335, (ii) tax 0.196, and (iii) revenue growth 0.195 are determinants of funding, but they cannot reduce financial distress. If the manager decides to finance using these three factors, it will not affect the company's financial distress.

1. INTRODUCTION

The trade industry is one of the pioneering contributors to Indonesia's National GDP. The Ministry of Trade said the retail trade subsector's contribution in the first quarter of 2020 was still high with a contribution percentage of 12.83% with a contribution from the consumption side of 57.31% (Pos 2020). This high contribution, despite the unstable world economic conditions, indicates that retail trading companies are able to boost Indonesia's economic growth. The high contribution from the retail trading company is due to the fact that the company's products are classified as primary products, which almost all people need the products to be traded. (Sih et al. 2019). In 2020 at this time, the government is encouraging retail trading companies to be the restorer of the economy which continues to

decline, because it is proven that it can still make a high contribution this year (Liliyah 2020). Retail trading companies must also continue to have good performance to achieve the mandate from the government. (Wicaksono et al. 2021).

A high contribution does not necessarily indicate that the company's financial condition is in good condition. BPS data as of September 2020 provided that 82.85% of revenue from trading companies fell during this pandemic (Indonesia 2020). The government has also attempted to stimulate various fiscal policies to ease and reduce the burden on all companies in Indonesia, from reducing the tax burden (tax deferral) for up to six months, deferring credit installments, and providing stimulus funds of Rp8.5 trillion to Rp22.5 trillion in February and March to facilitate and encourage growth of affected industrial companies (Indonesia 2020). Companies will not

depend on these funds during this pandemic. The company must determine the appropriate strategy to increase additional funds and create corporate value. (Hilman Hakim and Arnie 2019)

Companies must also be sufficient and fund all business operations to survive during the current pandemic. (Arifin et al. 2021, vol. 20, p.) If this crisis condition is not corrected and continues in the future, it is possible that trading companies will not be able to maintain their operational business. (Putra et al.) This condition will be dangerous for the country's economy and society. One way that companies can pursue is the determination of the right financial policy (financial decision). (Suyitno et al. 2020) Financial policy is a policy established by a company regarding funding decisions as an additional source of corporate funds and distribution of funds, both for internal and external parties to the company to continue and improve operational performance. The purpose of financial decisions is to create corporate value for external parties. (Maulida et al.)

There are three decisions in determining financial decisions, including: (i) investment decisions, and (ii) funding decisions, (iii) dividend policies. The determination of these three decisions is important for companies to make the right investment decisions, as well as the types of funding that are effective and appropriate in order to improve and restore the company's slumping performance, and not to have a negative impact on the company's finances in the future during a pandemic like today. First, investment decisions are related to the determination of the company's capital allocation to increase and optimize firm value. Second, the funding decision is the capital structure set by the manager which can be presented on the liabilities side of the statement of financial position (Wiagustini 2010; Darmayanti 2013). Financial decisions that are very important in the midst of this pandemic are funding decisions. (Lee and Chou 2019) Investment decisions do need to be taken into account when a company is over-funded, but this is not suitable to be the focus of a company's evaluation during a pandemic, which tends to lack of funds infusion. (Wbba and Pratomo)

Companies must decide which sources of funding to use while decreasing income and an unstable economy for the company's sustainability. Determining factors related to funding decisions must be determined

so that there are no errors in making funding decisions during this pandemic so as not to result in less beneficial funding costs for the company. (Yusnita et al. 2017) stated that profitability, sales growth, and taxes as macroeconomic factors have a significant effect on the determination of funding policies. Profitability is the company's ability to generate profits. (Nagar et al. 2019) The profit generated will be allocated as retained earnings or directly used for investment. (Ardiansyah and Hartono 2014) show different things, that profitability as an indicator of a company's ability to generate profits has a negative effect on funding decisions.

Sales growth is also very influential in determining the company's funding decisions and capital allocation for external parties, because it can increase the company's profit growth which can influence decisions on the use of resources to be used, as well as investment and dividend policies. (Anon.). Sales growth indicates a good performance and as an indicator to determine the sustainability of the company in the future. (Irmadaryani et al. 2019) This item is of course very important to be evaluated in every company in the midst of a pandemic so that it can determine the prospects for the company's future business sustainability (going concern). (Fawaid Ridwan and Supian 2021). The results of (Banun 2015) study state that sales growth has no effect on company funding decisions. These results are in line with research by (Ardiansyah and Hartono 2014; Ratri and Christianti 2017) which states that sales growth has no effect (has a negative effect) on funding decisions.

Company size can also be a determining factor for funding decisions with indicators of total assets, stock market value, and average total sales and asset levels (Seftianne and Handayani 2011). Companies that have different sizes will certainly determine the proportion of funding differently.

Asset structure must also be evaluated by managers in determining funding decisions and dividend policy. (Deegan 2014). Asset structure shows the company's investment in the form of fixed assets which can be measured through a comparison between fixed assets and the company's total assets. (Agustin et al. 2021) The structure of fixed assets has a significant effect on corporate debt. Also, the asset structure, growth, and profitability of the company have a positive effect on the company's capital structure. Others

research states that growth and asset structure do not affect funding decisions. (Naveed et al. 2020)

Determination of funding decisions related to determining the company's capital structure and sources of funds will certainly have an impact on the company's own financial distress in the midst of a pandemic. (Mahmood et al. 2018) defines financial distress (FD) as "... a situation in which firms face problems in fulfilling its contractual liabilities through its cash inflows". FD can occur if the amount of available cash presented through cash flow is not sufficient to pay off corporate bonds or liabilities. (Dewantara et al. 2021) The existence of this pandemic can further increase the company's financial distress due to decreased income so that it has the potential to go bankrupt. (Kusanti and Andayani 2015) states that financial distress is caused by internal and external factors. Internal factors that can affect the company's financial distress are the amount of debt and profit loss. The external factor that affects FD is the loan interest rate. (Roziq et al. 2020)

(Kristanti et al. 2016) state that corporate governance is indicated by five indicators (gender differences, location of directors, independent board, quality of CEOs and auditors) and financial ratios with six indicators (Leverage, Operating risk, size, current ratio, profitability, risk, PBV) determines the probability of financial distress in family firms or companies where each shareholder has a share ownership proportion of more than 25% which is listed on the IDX from 2008 to 2013. (Farida et al. 2019) The results of this study indicate that gender differences, independent boards, leverage, and current ratios, the location of directors, and the quality of CEOs affect the financial distress of Indonesian family firms. Operational risk, probability, and market, as well as the size and quality of auditors do not significantly affect the financial distress of the Indonesian family firm. (Nurhayati et al. 2017) explain the factors that can determine a company's financial distress related to financial ratios as a predictive tool for financial distress in basic industry and chemistry, showing current ratios, and ROA has a positive effect as a predictor of financial distress, while Debt to assets has a negative effect. Total Asset Turnover cannot predict the company's financial distress. (Ikpesu 2019) shows that revenue growth is also one of the factors that can determine a company's financial distress.

This study determines 7 factors in determining funding policy - company size, sales growth, profitability, asset structure, number of independent commissioners, number of directors, and taxes as external factors. (Winarno et al. 2021a) This study aims to determine the determinants of funding decisions that can reduce corporate financial distress. The addition of this external factor is to determine the effect of the fiscal stimulus set by the government to be able to reduce corporate financial distress or not. (Sumani and Roziq 2020).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Debt Financing

Funding decisions are capital structure decisions to fund the company's operations and investment decision (Jesilia and Purwaningsih 2020). Managers can decide the source of funds that will be used to fund the company's business operations during the next period. (Sitanggung 2012) defines a funding decision as a decision on sources of funds to finance the company's operations and investment, both from internal and external funds. Funding decisions are also a substitute for future profits if the company experiences a loss or lacks funds to distribute to stakeholders. (Dewi Rachma et al. 2019)

Financial Distress

Financial Distress (FD) or financial difficulties can occur if the company is unable to use cash efficiently. (Rachmi et al. 2020). FD can also occur, when a company cannot pay off all bonds due to a lack of funding so that no resources can be guaranteed or paid to pay off the company's obligations to creditors. This financial distress causes total liabilities to exceed the company's total assets (Nurhayati et al. 2017). Total liabilities that exceed total assets indicate that the company is less effective in using its assets to generate cash inflows for the company. Financial distress can be shown by negative net profit, using the long-term debt to assets ratio, and debt to assets as a means of detecting financial distress (Platt and Platt 2002).

Pecking Order Theory

This theory explains the order in which the company's funding sources can be used and determined, either from internal sources of funds (retained earnings) or external in the form of debt, and finally the issuance of new equity. (Kustono

et al. 2021). Companies that follow the order of this theory in their funding decisions, according to the signaling theory, this gives a signal of good company prospects in the future. Profitable companies prefer internal rather than external sources of funds. This is because the issuance of new securities will lower the share price so that it can reduce the value of the company which can have an impact on the level of funds the company will receive in the future (investment). (Paramita et al. 2020). When using internal funds (retained earnings), the company does not need to pay deposits to outside parties.

Agency Theory

Agency theory explains that related to the difference in motivation between managers and investors or owners, this conflict of interest can actually harm one party. (Kustono 2020) Therefore, agents and principles influence each other to achieve their motivation. This difference results in asymmetric information (information gaps) provided by managers not in accordance with the needs of external parties. (Widyaningdyah 2001) also states that agents will provide information that is symmetrical to market needs only if there is incentive or supervision from the principle. (Winarno et al. 2021b).

Signaling Theory

This theory is a response to agent theory which explains the conflict of interest between agents and principles. (Rachman 2016) explains that this signal theory is a signal given by managers to investors in the form of presenting financial information to eliminate conflicts or motivational trade-off between management as an agent and investors/owners as a principle as a result of agency theory. (Roziq et al. 2019)

The results of research from (Akingunola and Oyetayo 2014) show that profitability affects the capital structure (funding) of the company. (Jesilia and Purwaningsih 2020) stated that profitability has a significant effect on funding decisions. The results of research from (Selviana and Badjra 2018) show that profitability has a negative effect on funding decisions.

The results of research by (Magdalena et al. 2017) state that company size has no effect on the company's capital structure. (Selviana and Badjra 2018) produce different research results which show company size has a positive effect on funding decisions. (Yusnita et al. 2017) states that sales growth has a positive effect on company funding decisions. (Banun 2015) states that sales

growth has no effect on company funding decisions. (Putra and Prabowo 2019)

Taxes affect corporate funding, because taxes can reduce corporate profits. (Nawang Sari et al. 2020) Taxes are influenced by interest which can reduce corporate taxes. (Winarno et al. 2021a) The higher the corporate tax, the more potential it is to use debt. (Iriansyah and Dana 2013) taxes have an effect on funding decisions, but this is not the same as the results of research from (Nasimi 2016). (Rosyida 2018) stated that free cash flow is the akas akas after all company liabilities have been paid, has no influence on the capital structure. (Rahman and Triani 2014) show that free cash flow has a positive effect on funding decisions.

Asset structure can also influence the determination of funding decisions. The larger the resulting asset structure, will result the higher debt of company. This condition is in accordance with the research of (Riyadi 2014; Banun 2015) but it is different from the research results of (Kartika 2016) which state there is no influence between asset structure and funding decisions.

This is in line with the results of research from (Vakilifard et al. 2011) which shows that the number of boards of commissioners has a positive effect on funding decisions, but not with (Yulianto 2010) which state there is no relationship.

The number of independent commissioners who do not have any rights over the company because they are not part of the shareholders can also influence funding decisions. This is explained in the research of (Shafana 2016), while (Yulianto 2010; Waworuntu et al. 2014) did not result a relationship between the numbers of independent commissioners on funding decisions.

The hypothesis from the results of previous research regarding the independent and dependent variables can be formulated, as follows:

H1 = Funding factor affects funding

H2 = Funding factors affect financial distress

H3 = Funding factor affects financial distress through funding decisions

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The object of research related to the Analysis of Determining Factors for Funding Decisions of Retail Trading Company in order to reduce Company Financial Distress is the Retail Trading Company. The data source used is

secondary Data, namely financial statements from retail trading companies listed on the IDX from 20188 to 2019.

The data population of this study is all trading companies listed on the IDX until 2019 with complete financial reports. The sample selection uses purposive sampling by determining whether companies are registered or not on the IDX, because there are several companies that do not provide complete data needed by researchers.

The data collection technique used by researchers is a literature study using secondary data sources, namely financial reports, annual reports, and information related to capital allocation on the company's website from 2016 to 2019. Data analysis method is a method used by researchers to analyze the data obtained so as to produce information that can be processed. The method of analysis in this study uses the SME model with SPSS AMOS 26 and the analysis used in this study, among others:

1. Content analysis is conducted to analyze the content of secondary data sources related to the research topic
2. Multivariate Normality Test is used to test and answer complex questions or more than one independent and dependent variable

Hypothesis testing using Path Analysis is used to examine the relationship between the factors that have been determined by the researcher on the determination of capital allocation which can reduce financial stress for the company. This research consists of independent, intervening, and dependent variables. There are eight variables in this study, among others:

A. Sales Growth (X1)

Companies with stable sales growth prefer to use external funds. The use of external funds or debt is chosen because the company's ability to pay off these external funds is higher than that of companies that have unstable sales growth. The formula that is used to calculate this variable:

$$\text{Sales Growth} = \frac{St - St-1}{St-1}$$

B. Firm Size (X2)

Company size is one of the determinants of funding decisions. Firm size tends to be measured by the total assets owned. A higher total assets of the company, it indicates a higher the size of the company. Large company size will require large funding as well to maintain and finance high total

assets. Company size in this study is measured by Ln total assets that was also used by (Selviana and Badjra 2018) in their research:

$$\text{Firm Size} = \text{Ln Total Assets}$$

C. Structure of Assets (X3)

Asset structure is the ratio of total current and non-current assets. Asset structure can influence funding decisions because it determines the amount of funds needed to maintain fixed assets and purchase current assets of the company. Asset structure can be measured by comparing total fixed assets divided by total assets

$$\text{Structure of assets} = \frac{\text{Total Fixed Assets}}{\text{Total Assets}}$$

D. Profitability (X4)

Indicators for profitability in this study use NPM. The use of NPM was chosen because it shows the company's ability to generate net income, because funding decisions not only consider operational activities, but also external factors must also be considered.

$$\text{NPM} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Sales}}$$

E. Taxes (X5)

Taxes also need to be taken into account in determining funding decisions because they affect the amount of net income of the company so that it will directly affect the use of sources of funds that will be used by the company.

$$\text{Taxes} = \frac{\text{EAT} - \text{EBIT}}{\text{EBIT}}$$

F. Board of Director (X6)

The indicator of the board of directors as one of the elements of good governance in this study is to use the amount presented in the company's annual report

G. Independent commissioners (X7)

The number of independent commissioners as supervisors which can increase transparency of the board of directors and as an element of good corporate governance according to the number presented in the company's annual report

H. Funding Decision (Y)

Funding decisions are company decisions regarding sources of funds to be used for

operational activities and company investment quality. The source of these funds can come from internal companies shown on retained or external earnings (debt) and issuance of new equity. Managers must determine the right and most efficient resources so as not to generate excessive funding costs. The formula used for funding decisions, is:

$$\text{Debt to Equity} = \frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Equity}}$$

I. Financial Distress (Z)

The formula used to measure a company's financial distress is a negative EPS value. A negative EPS indicates a negative company value in the market so this can be a factor in a company going bankrupt or experiencing financial distress.

$$\text{EPS} = \frac{\text{Net Income} - \text{Preferred Dividend}}{\text{Average Outstanding Shares}}$$

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Sample data obtained from Retail Service Companies during 2018 and 2019 are normally distributed. This normal distribution is indicated by a kurtosis value of $2.920 < 3$ so that the data is normally distributed multivariate. After the normality test was carried out, the sample data were analyzed using path analysis. The results of the path test or path analysis between the independent variables on funding (intervening) show a direct effect between the Net Profit Margin on funding of -11,515, so that from these results H_0a is accepted, H_1a is rejected.

Table 1. Path Analysis (Direct Effect)

Path	Direct Effect		
	Coefficient	P Value	R Square
NPM → DER	-11.515	0.021	0.288
Assets Structure → DER	-1.284	0.301	
SG → DER	0.195	0.733	
Board of Director → DER	-0.419	0.013	
Independent Commissioner → DER	-0.064	0.884	

LnTAssets → DER	0.335	0.083
Taxes → DER	0.196	0.773
DER → FD	-4.359	0.640
NPM → FD	1185.684	0.01
Assets Structure → FD	23.463	0.74
SG → FD	-17.023	0.61
Board of Director → FD	4.227	0.69
Independent Commissioner → FD	86.592	0.01
Ln T Assets → FD	-23.789	0.42
Taxes → FD	12.455	0.31

Source: Processed by researcher, SPSS AMOS 26

The second factor also shows the negative effect of asset structure on funding with a path coefficient of -1.284. The negative effect also occurs on the number of the Board of Directors with a coefficient value of -0.419, and -0.064 Independent Commissioners. Factors that have a positive effect on funding decisions are revenue growth with a coefficient of 0.195, company size of 0.335, and tax of 0.196.

The direct influence between the determinants of funding decisions on financial distress shows that there are 5 factors that have a positive effect on financial distress, while the other two factors have no effect (negative influence). The first factor that has a positive direct effect on FD is Net Profit Margin with a coefficient value of 1185,684, Asset Structure of 23,463, the number of Directors 4,227, the number of Independent Commissioners of 86,592, and 12,445 taxes. Sales growth factor and company size have a significant negative effect with the values of -17.023 and -23,789. The contribution of the influence of the determinants mentioned above was 28.8%.

The path test results above show that the factors that influence funding are more influential on the level of corporate financial distress with the influence of determining factors (independent variables) of 47.9% than the direct influence of the financial distress decision. NPM has no effect on financing decisions, indicating that the amount

of net income is not the basis for the company to make funding decisions, either from internal or external, and the issuance of securities. Asset structure also has no effect on retail trading companies in making funding policies. The corporate governance factor represented by the number of directors and commissioners also has no effect on the formation of funding.

Table 2. Path Analysis (Indirect Effect)

Path	Indirect Effect	
	Coefficient	P Value
NPM – DER – FD	50.188	0.806
Assets Structure – DER – FD	5.597	0.670
SG – DER – FD	-0.850	0.890
Board of Director → DER – FD	1.826	0.646
Independent Commissioners – DF – FD	0.280	0.783
LnTAssets – DER – FD	-1.461	0.646
Taxes – DER – FD	-0.854	0.651

Source: Processed by researcher, SPSS AMOS 26

The indirect effect between the independent variable as a factor in funding decisions through funding decisions, has an effect on the company's financial distress. It shows 4 factors that show a positive and insignificant relationship ($p > 0,05$) through the funding intervening variable, among others; (i) NPM, (ii) Assets Structure, (iii) Board of director, and (iv) Independent Commissioners. Factors that have a negative and insignificant ($p > 0,05$) effect on financial distress with intervening funding decisions include; (i) company size -1,461, (ii) Tax -0,854, and (iii) Sales Growth with a value of -0,850.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

The results of this study indicate; (i) company size 0.335, (ii) tax 0.196, and (iii) revenue growth 0.195 are determinants of funding, but they

cannot reduce financial distress. If the manager decides to finance using these three factors, it will not affect the company's financial distress.

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